

Complexes of Silicon(IV) with Benzoin, Furoin and Pyridoin

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Silicon and organosilicon derivatives of benzoin, furoin and pyridoin have been synthesised and their structures have been assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral (ir, uv and nmr) data. Chelated structures are proposed for the resulting derivatives in which the ligands acted as bidentate reagents. Cationic complexes are formed when silicon tetrachloride reacts with the ligands whereas the complexes formed by the reaction of dialkyl dichlorosilane and dialkyl chlorosilane with the ligands are non electrolytes in DMF.

A survey of the literature reveals that no study has been made of the complexing of silicon by benzoin, furoin and pyridoin. It was therefore considered of interest to synthesise some new silicon derivatives of bidentate α -hydroxyketones and study their characteristics by elemental analysis and spectral (ir, uv and nmr) measurements.

Experimental

Silicon tetrachloride, dimethyl chlorosilane, dimethyl dichlorosilane, benzoin and pyridin-2-carboxaldehyde (Fluka AG, Switzerland) were used as such. Furfural (Hopkin and Williams) was purified¹.

Preparation of ligands and complexes: Furoin and pyridoin were prepared by standard methods². The silicon chelates were prepared as follow. To a solution of absolute methanol (100 ml) and the ligand (0.06 mol) was added dropwise a solution of silicon (0.02 mol) tetrachloride in the same solvent (100 ml) (in cases of using dimethyl dichlorosilane and dimethyl chlorosilane, 0.03 and 0.06 mole were used respectively) with stirring in N_2 atmosphere and the solution was refluxed for 1 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from a warm methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam sp-2000 spectrophotometer, uv spectra ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-5}$ solution) on a sp-800 double beam spectrophotometer at room temperature and 1H nmr spectra on a Bruker WH-90 instrument. Conductivity measurements were carried out with a M.C.3 conductivity bridge at room temperature using $10^{-3} M$ DMF solutions of the compounds.

C, H and N analyses were obtained using a Carlo Erba-Strumentazione 1106 analyzer. The silicon and chloride were determined according to the reported method³.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The ir spectra of benzoin and furoin⁴ show a band at 3400 cm^{-1} due to intramolecularly bonded alcoholic OH stretching which disappears on complexation indicating thereby that alcoholic oxygen is bonded to the silicon. A strong band at 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O) in benzoin shifts to 1665 cm^{-1} (in furoin C=O band appears at 1675 cm^{-1} and shifts to 1650 cm^{-1}) on complexation, which in turn, indicates C=O...Si coordination. The greater the shift of the band due to $\nu_{C=O}$ to longer wavelengths, the stronger the C=O...Si bond⁶. But in the present study it is observed that the $\nu_{C=O}$ vibration is very little affected by chelation (only a small shift towards lower frequency occurring) indicating that the chelation is not so strong. The bands at $1020-1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes may be assigned to the ν_{Si-O-C} vibration⁶, and there is no such band in this region for the ligands.

The ir spectrum of the pyridoin shows a strong broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} and no absorption due to carbonyl group as would have been expected. The nmr spectrum of the pyridoin shows only one broad signal at $\delta 12.8$ due to two protons exchangeable with D_2O . Other signal at $\delta 8.5-7.57$ are typical aromatical aromatic protons of the pyridyl group. These data suggest that pyridoin exists in a chelate transendiol structure,

Such conclusion is in agreement with that reported by Buchler *et al.*⁷.

The disappearance of the ν_{OH} band at 3400 cm^{-1} indicates the involvement of the alcoholic

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	M.p.** °C	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Molar cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
				C	H	N	Si	Cl	
1.	Si(L) ₂ Cl	182-84	White	72.06 (72.34)	4.93 (4.77)	—	4.12 (4.04)	5.15 (5.05)	68.0
2.	(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L) ₂	258-60	White	74.52 (74.96)	5.44 (5.87)	—	5.93 (5.86)	—	8.0
3.	(CH ₃) ₂ HSiL	282-86	White	71.33 (71.07)	6.82 (6.70)	—	10.53 (10.40)	—	11.8
4.	Si(L') ₂ Cl	300	Black	56.77 (56.56)	3.76 (3.32)	—	4.71 (4.42)	5.71 (5.53)	75.5
5.	(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L') ₂	153-55	Dark brown	60.29 (59.98)	4.71 (4.57)	—	6.25 (6.39)	—	8.5
6.	(CH ₃) ₂ HSiL'	160-62	Black	57.37 (57.57)	5.27 (5.63)	—	11.01 (11.24)	—	4.7
7.	Si(L'') ₂ Cl	172-74	Yellow	61.22 (61.49)	3.97 (3.87)	12.36 (11.95)	3.94 (4.00)	5.22 (5.00)	69.0
8.	(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L'') ₂	208-10	Yellow	64.73 (64.44)	5.31 (4.99)	11.29 (11.56)	5.98 (5.81)	—	9.5
9.	(CH ₃) ₂ HSiL''	200-02	Yellow	62.07 (61.73)	6.21 (5.92)	10.64 (10.28)	10.12 (10.33)	—	7.2

**All complexes are soluble in one of the organic solvents : DMSO, DMF, EtOH and acetone.

oxygen atom in the bond formation with silicon through deprotonation. This type of bonding is confirmed by the appearance of a new band at 620-630 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{Si-O}. The increase in frequency of the C=N upon complexation may be attributed to removal of the hydrogen bond, whereas the new band at 1635 cm⁻¹ in all the silicon-pyridoin complexes may be assigned to C=O...Si coordination.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the silicon-pyridoin complexes show a new signal at δ 3.6 which can be related to the aliphatic proton resulting from the return of the ligand to keto-form.

The uv spectra of the benzoin, furoin and pyridoin show a band at 275 nm (ε_{max}=9000 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), 285 nm (ε_{max}=10400) and 280 nm (ε_{max}=7600), which can be associated with π-π* electronic transition. On chelation the wavelength of this absorption does not vary significantly. The lower values of molar conductivity for the complexes (Sl. nos. 2, 3, 5, 6, 8 and 9) show their non-electrolytic nature. However, molar conductivities of the

cationic complexes (Sl. nos. 1, 4 and 7) lying in the range 68-75 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ correspond to 1:1 electrolytes⁸⁻¹¹.

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